

Vapour Pressures of some Mono- and Di-Alkyl Substituted Aliphatic Amides at Different Temperatures¹

Ram Gopal and Sharaf Abbas Rizvi

Vapour pressures of N-methylacetamide, N-methyl-propionamide, N, N-dimethylformamide, N, N-dimethylacetamide, and N, N-diethylformamide, have been determined in the temperature range 30- 90°C. The values of the heats of vaporization, obtained from the v.p. data, appear to be larger for the mono-substituted compounds than those for the di-substituted ones. The vapour pressures of the former are also lower. These facts confirm a stronger molecular interaction in the mono-substituted amides.

Some solvents of high dielectric constant such as formamide, N-methylformamide (NMF), N-methylacetamide (NMA), and N-methylpropionamide (NMP) as well as some N, N-dialkylsubstituted amides of this family, have been attracting the attention of a large number of workers in view of the special structural features and hydrogen bonding. A number of their physical properties have been reported in the literature during the last few years^{2,3,4,5}. It appears, however, that a systematic study of the vapour pressure of many of them is still lacking and, in general little attention seems to have been paid in this direction. Vapour pressures of formamide^{6,7}, dimethylformamide⁸ and of NHA⁹ have been reported at a few temperatures. In view of the utility of the vapour pressure data, it was considered desirable to undertake a study of the vapour pressures of these solvents at different temperatures. The present communication reports the vapour pressures of NMA, NMP, N, N-dimethylformamide, N, N-methylformamide and N, N-dimethyl-formamide at different temperatures in 30-90° range.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Purification of the solvents*: The samples, supplied by M/s Eastman Kodak (sp. cond. $\approx 10^{-4}$ mho) were treated with freshly ignited quicklime and distilled in vacuum, the middle fraction being retained. This fraction, for every liquid, was again treated with freshly ignited quicklime and then vacuum-distilled. The whole process

1. Work supported by the C.S.I.R., India.
2. Dawson and coworkers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1986; *ibid*, 1957, **79**, 4652.
3. Bass and coworkers, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 503 & 509.
4. Leader and Gormley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5731.
5. Gopal and Rizvi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 179.
6. Hodgman and others, "Handbook of Physics and Chemistry", Chemical Rubber Publishing Company, Cleveland, Ohio, 1962-63, p. 2458.
7. Somsen and Coops, *Rec. Trav. Chem.*, 1965, **84**, 988.
8. Lange, "Handbook of Chemistry", MacGraw Hill Book Company, New York, 1961, p. 1428.
9. Aihara, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (Japan), 1952, **73**, 855-57.

was repeated until, in each case, the conductance was reduced to about 10^{-5} — 10^{-7} mho. The samples were stored in coloured bottles and kept in a dry box. As far as possible, these were used soon after distillation.

(b) *Measurement of vapour pressure*: The vapour pressure was measured in all-sealed pyrex glass manometer without any stop-cock. Although the absence of stop-cocks in the manometer, or anywhere in the measuring system, made the handling of the apparatus difficult no doubt, but this ensured security of the vacuum. In later experiments, a stop-cock in the manometer was used but there was no certainty about complete security of the apparatus against leakage when the temperature rose and the high vacuum grease in the stop-cock softened (this forced several repetitions and loss of time). The original manometer, with accessories for drying and degassing, is given in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

As may be seen from Fig. 1, a battery of three tubes, two of which (D & E) contained some freshly ignited quicklime and the third (C) contained the purified solvent, was sealed to one arm of the manometer. The other arm of the manometer was sealed to the vacuum line (the pressure inside the line, as shown by the vacuostat, was less than 10^{-4} mm and since the mercury diffusion pump was running, the pressure could be as low as 10^{-5} – 10^{-6} mm) as indicated in Fig. 1. The liquid sample in C was frozen in liquid oxygen and then the manometer and accessories were thoroughly evacuated. The vacuum was then cut off and the frozen sample was melted for degassing. Again the liquid sample was frozen, the manometer connected to the vacuum line and evacuated. The whole operation was repeated until the degassing of the sample was complete. Then, finally, the manometer was sealed off at A and separated from the vacuum line, keeping the liquid sample frozen. The two limbs of the manometer were isolated from each other by sealing the manometer tube at B. The complete unit i.e., the manometer and the tubes, were kept in an air thermostat whose temperature could be regulated to within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. The readings on the manometer scale were read through a narrow vertical glass window which could be closed with a sliding wooden strip when the reading was not being taken. The cathetometer could not be used due to the indistinct image formed in the telescope and so the readings were taken with a naked eye. The bore of the manometer tube was more than 6 mm. and so the capillary effect was negligible. After the thermostat had acquired

the desired temperature, an hour was allowed for the attainment of equilibrium and then the reading was taken. Observations were made both when the temperature was rising and when it was falling, usually at 10° intervals. The complete procedure was repeated with the same sample and with different samples, to make sure that the readings were reproducible.

In order to check the effect of the traces of water which may be present, the sample in tube C was distilled to one of the two tubes D or E, containing quicklime. The sample was left there overnight and then redistilled to C while D or E (as the case may be) was cut off. The measurements were repeated as described above. Usually no significant changes were observed. In the case of a significant change, the sample was dehydrated again (in E or D) and the process repeated. Usually this operation was not required.

As a check on the accuracy of our procedure and reliability of the data, vapour pressure of aniline (a liquid of low vapour pressure as the liquids under study) was measured at different temperatures. After a thorough dehydration over quicklime (this required two to three days), a close agreement was obtained between the observed values and those given in the literature as can be seen from Table I.

TABLE I
Vapour pressure of aniline at different temperatures

	Vapour pressure in mm. of Hg at						
	35°	50°	60°	70°	80°	90°	98°
Observed ...	1.0	2.0	4.	9.5	16.0	29.0	40.0 mm
Literature ...	1.0	—	—	10.0			40.0 mm
value*	at			at			at
... 34.2°				69.4°			98.6°

* From Hodgman and others, "Handbook of Physics and Chemistry", Chemical Rubber Publishing Company, Cleveland, Ohio, 1962-63, Edn. 44, p. 2475.

The vapour pressure of different liquids, determined by the procedure given above, are recorded in Table II. All the pressure readings have been reduced to 0°C. The estimated standard error in measurements does not exceed ± 0.5 mm.

TABLE II

	Vapour Pressure in mm. of Hg at						
Compound	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°	90°
NMF		Decomposes					
NMA	—	0.5	0.5	1.5	3.5	8.0	13.5
NMP	0.5	1.0	1.5	3.0	4.5	7.0	14.0
N,N-DMA	5.5	10.0	16.0	26.0	42.5	66.5	102.
N,N-DMF	5.5	10.0	17.5	29.5	46.5	72.5	109.0
	(5.45)*	(10.09)*	(17.45)*	(29.10)*	(46.8)*	(72.5)*	(109.1)*
N,N-DEF	2.0	3.5	6.5	11.5	19.0	31.5	48.5

* Estimated from the data given in ref. 8,

DISCUSSION

It may be noted from Table II, that the vapour pressures of N-alkylsubstituted amides are lower than those of the N, N-disubstituted amides, indicating a stronger molecular interaction in the former than in the latter. Among the disubstituted compounds, the radical weight of the substituent appears to have a pronounced effect; the heavier substituent reduces the v.p. considerably e.g., in DMF and DEF.

The plot of $\log p$ against $1/T$ is almost a straight line in each case as is clear from Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

The plots correspond to the following eqns.:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{NMA : } \log P = 11.063 - \frac{3606}{T} \\
 \text{DMA : } \log P = 8.510 - \frac{2360}{T} \\
 \text{DEF : } \log P = 8.732 - \frac{2557}{T} \\
 \text{NMP : } \log P = 8.970 - \frac{2840}{T} \\
 \text{DMF : } \log P = 8.609 - \frac{2382}{T}
 \end{array}$$

The approximate enthalpies of vaporisation, obtained from the slopes of these curves, are 16.5, 13.0, 10.9, 10.8, and 11.7 Kcals-mole for NMA, NMP, DMA, DMF, and DEF respectively. It is obvious that the enthalpy data also indicate a stronger molecular interaction in the mono-substituted compounds. This is specially pronounced in NMA, perhaps due to ease of forming *cis*- and *trans*-forms¹⁰, due to the latter, NMA is known to have linear association, leading to chain polymers, specially at low temperatures. Further comments are withheld until more data have been obtained.

Financial assistance, given by the Society of the Sigma XI and RESA of America, for buying special chemicals, is gratefully acknowledged.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY, INDIA.

Received, November 8, 1966.